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IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D5.1 DIGILAB Implementation Plan

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable D5.1 entitled “DIGILAB Implementation Plan” is part of E-RIHS work package WP5 “Access and digital services of E-RIHS” and more specifically the task T5.1 “Steps towards building DIGILAB”. This deliverable aims at: (a) formulating a shared vision for the role of DIGILAB, and (b) proposing a road map for the implementation of DIGILAB. It defines the place and the role of DIGILAB in E-RIHS (see section 1) and presents the updated version of the conceptual plan and overall schema for DIGILAB (see section 2). The implementation road map deliverable has been carried out based on the results gather during the E-RIHS community workshops (see section 3) and the survey on existing resources and services for DIGILAB (see section 4). The implementation strategy is developed in 4 different layers and a 5-year tentative timeline is outlined along with a Business Process Model and cost analysis (see section 5).

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

WHAT IS DIGILAB?	7
1 DEFINING THE PLACE AND THE ROLE OF DIGILAB	8
1.1 RELATED PAST WORKS	8
1.2 CRITICAL POINTS	8
2 UPDATED VERSION OF THE CONCEPTUAL PLAN OF DIGILAB	9
2.1 FROM RESEARCH QUESTIONS TO KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION	9
2.2 OVERALL SCHEMA	10
3 E-RIHS COMMUNITY WORKSHOPS	12
3.1 WORKSHOPS OBJECTIVES.....	12
3.2 WORKSHOPS FORMAT.....	12
3.3 RESULTS FROM THE WORKSHOPS	13
4 SURVEY ON EXISTING RESOURCES AND SERVICES THAT COULD SUPPORT E-RIHS DIGILAB INFRASTRUCTURE AND USER NEEDS	14
4.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE SURVEY	14
4.2 SURVEY FORMAT AND SECTIONS.....	14
4.3 SURVEY RESULTS	14
4.3.A. <i>Data Management and Data Access Policy</i>	15
4.3.B. <i>Digital infrastructure</i>	17
4.3.C. <i>Digital Resources for Heritage Science</i>	18
4.3.D. <i>Digital Services for data analysis, interpretation, enrichment and reuse</i>	18
5 IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY	20
5.1 DIGILAB IN THE FUTURE EUROPEAN COLLABORATIVE CLOUD FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE.....	20
5.2 DIGILAB AND THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD	21
5.3 DIGILAB IMPLEMENTATION LAYERS	22
<i>Layer 0. DIGILAB Community Building and Initial Digital Services Identification</i>	23
<i>Layer 1. Managing the Data Lifecycle</i>	24
<i>Layer 2. Towards an Integrated Virtual Research Environment</i>	28
<i>Layer 3. Towards a E-RIHS Knowledge Base</i>	30
<i>Data Analysis Perspectives, IA and Ethics</i>	33
5.4 TENTATIVE TIMELINE.....	34
<i>Year 1: Foundation and Planning</i>	34
<i>Year 2: Initial Implementation and Testing</i>	34
<i>Year 3: Expansion and Refinement</i>	35
<i>Year 4: Full-Scale Implementation</i>	35
<i>Year 5: Optimisation and Evaluation</i>	35
6 BUSINESS PROCESS MODELLING AND COST ANALYSIS	35
6.1 PROCEDURE FOR MODELLING CULTURAL HERITAGE DIGITIZATION PROCESSES.....	36
ANNEX	37
USE CASE ON COST ESTIMATION OF A DIGITAL SERVICE: A PILOT ON ILLUMINATED MANUSCRIPTS HUB.....	37
REFERENCES	43

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Positing DIGILAB in the E-RIHS network.....	11
Figure 2: Responders from Institutions - members of an E-RIHS National Node.	14
Figure 3: Solutions adopted, at institutional or national level for hosting, managing and maintaining data repositories.....	17
Figure 4: Types of digital resources that are available for educational or working applications.	18
Figure 5: Existing tools were mentioned in relation to the following services for data analysis, interpretation, enrichment and re-use.	19
Figure 6: Digital resources or services that are intended to be offered in DIGILAB by E-RIHS National Nodes.	19
Figure 7: Focus on the metadata/paradata and data lifecycle in the conceptual schema.....	25
Figure 8: Focus on the digital services in the conceptual schema.	28
Figure 9: Focus on the knowledge base in the conceptual schema.	31

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Workshop overview.....	12
Table 2. Institutions promoting open access to publications and FAIR data and encouraging the publication of data in open repositories, by countries	16
Table 3. Layer 0: Key needs for community building (KN_Ax)	24
Table 4. Layer 1: Key needs for managing the data cycle (KN_Bx)	26
Table 5. Layer 1: key needs for the data indexing and enrichment (KN_Cx).....	27
Table 6. Layer 2: Key needs for Virtual Research Environment (KN_Dx).....	29
Table 7. Layer 3: Key needs for research workflow design (KN_Ex)	32
Table 8. Layer 3: key needs for data analysis and Knowledge discovery (KN_Fx)	33

ABBREVIATIONS

AGATO	ArtGArden Decision Support Tool (https://agato.kikirpa.be/about/info/story-agato-where-agato)
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ARCHLAB	ARCHive LABoratory: Access platform that brings together organized scientific information in largely unpublished datasets from archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/).
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CH	Cultural Heritage
CIDOC CRM	Conceptual Reference Model of the International Committee for Documentation (https://www.cidoc-crm.org/)
CLIMPACTH	Climate Impact on Built Heritage (https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/research-groups/arches/built-heritage/climpacth/)
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, and Delete
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HESCIDA	Heritage Science Data Archive, https://hescida.kikirpa.be
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
E-RIHS NN	E-RIHS National Node
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIXLAB	FIXed LABoratory: Access platform that brings together fixed research facilities and associated scientific experience of their staff that develop and maintain sophisticated state-of-the-art instrumentation for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/)
HERIE	HERIE is a digital decision-supporting platform providing remote access to data manipulation tools and to quantitative assessment of risks to heritage assets. The platform is organised in the framework of ten independent modules corresponding to ten agents of deterioration (https://herie.pl/)
HS	Heritage Science
IP	Implementation Phase
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science (H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1, GA No. 871034, https://www.iperionhs.eu)
MOLAB	Mobile LABoratory: Access platform that brings together European laboratories offering state-of-the-art mobile equipment and related competencies, for in-situ non-destructive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments and sites (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
SENENSE	Spatial hEritage scieNce oNline Sensor Environment
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
Viewer NDP	3D Viewer developed in the Digital Data working group for the Notre-Dame de Paris research (Abergel, 2023)

WHAT IS DIGILAB?

DIGILAB is the DIGital LABoratory of E-RIHS. It is a socio-technical platform aiming to digitally connect stakeholders such as data producers and service providers with heritage objects and multidisciplinary studies. This platform will provide services for centralising, curating, processing, visualising, and making accessible data on heritage science, facilitating and fostering collaborative activities such as scientific study, conservation, restoration, and knowledge dissemination. Simply put, DIGILAB gathers, curates, and manages data produced by the other E-RIHS laboratories (ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB), but it also generates its own data and knowledge. DIGILAB provides services and tools within a virtual research environment that allow for advanced scientific interpretation, visualisation, analysis, and the creation of new data.

DIGILAB will primary feature three layers of services: the management of the data lifecycle, the creation of a collaborative virtual research environment, and a cumulative knowledge base. Additionally, two transversal components will be integral to DIGILAB's initiatives: digital infrastructure setup services and training in digital literacy development. By promoting shared protocols and harmonised workflows, DIGILAB aspires to become the reference point for scientific documentation of heritage objects for conservation, restoration, and dissemination scenarios, thereby accompanying the transformation of this field into a more data-driven discipline.

Acting in strong interaction with FIXLAB, MOLAB, and ARCHLAB, DIGILAB will provide an integrated framework for managing digital-driven research on cultural heritage while storing detailed information on adopted research protocols, including scientific inquiries, as well as the tools and methods utilised for various application contexts. This information will be progressively structured into a knowledge base exploitable by the entire heritage science community through both human and artificial intelligence lenses, opening heritage science to new large-scale data production and analysis scenarios.

In alignment with the principles of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and methods, DIGILAB is committed to integrating services and infrastructure that enhance connections between research projects, data, and collaborative opportunities. This integration will create a cohesive and supportive research environment, ensuring long-term accessibility and usability of research outputs. By consolidating metadata from existing national services (e.g. Digital.CSIC or HAL) along with broader repositories (e.g. Zenodo), DIGILAB will facilitate transnational searching and provide researchers with a cohesive view of heritage science assets.

DIGILAB acknowledges the integral role that humanistic inquiry plays in the interpretation and valorisation of cultural heritage. This inclusion ensures that the platform not only serves scientific and technical needs but also embraces the cultural and historical contexts essential for a comprehensive understanding of heritage objects.

The development of DIGILAB aligns with the broader E-RIHS digital infrastructure expansion, enhancing connections between research projects, data, and collaborative opportunities. This initiative will be supported by national digital infrastructure efforts aimed at developing interoperable services and digital opportunities, creating a network of heritage science resources. DIGILAB will also align with broader initiatives like the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), expanding the digital infrastructure to support a wider range of cultural heritage projects.

As it grows, DIGILAB will provide a centralised platform for discussion, data discovery, and tool sharing, fostering greater collaboration among researchers, institutions, and stakeholders. This collaborative environment will drive innovation and advance the field of heritage science. By ensuring that heritage data is well-managed, preserved, and accessible, DIGILAB will support robust research and analysis. Promoting FAIR data practices and open data management methods, DIGILAB will enable researchers to conduct more effective and efficient studies.

1 DEFINING THE PLACE AND THE ROLE OF DIGILAB

1.1 Related Past Works

Heritage science lacks shared protocols and standardised workflows, though some techniques have benefited from extensive collaborative development and established standards. However, many tools and methods remain experimental. One of the missions of E-RIHS is to provide services that streamline, harmonise, and formalise these processes, with a particular focus on fostering digital-centred approaches. During the preparatory phase of E-RIHS, the need for a fourth LAB platform, DIGILAB, emerged to capitalise on digital opportunities and enhance the potential of Heritage Science research in relation to MOLAB, FIXLAB, and ARCHLAB, as well as the broader heritage science community. Key milestones in developing DIGILAB included: DIGILAB's conceptual plan – presentation at Evora (January) and Paris (October) (Padfield and Degl'Innocenti, 2019), E-RIHS Scientific Strategy (2.0) (Bertrand et al. 2020), DIGILAB implementation strategy (Sorin, 2020) and Building DIGITAL (Sorin, 2021).

DIGILAB's vision was to create a digital platform for the E-RIHS community, offering integrated and interoperable digital resources (tools, services, data) to enhance research quality, coherence, efficiency, and data accessibility. As part of DIGILAB's conceptualisation, efforts are underway to develop a common strategy for generating, curating, and processing heritage science data. This strategy includes adopting internationally agreed procedures, canonical workflows and protocols, formalising knowledge representation through conceptual reference models, using common vocabularies and thesauri, and implementing FAIR data principles, with the goal of developing recommendations for what constitutes a FAIR Heritage science dataset and how we can create interoperable FAIR Digital Objects (FAIR DOs).

1.2 Critical Points

Defining DIGILAB within the E-RIHS has faced significant challenges, despite the widespread presence of digital data, workflows, and tools. One critical area is addressing the short- and long-term needs of the community, which encompass not only technical requirements but also methodological evolution and the new scientific vision regarding the role of digital and open data in heritage science. The question of open data and data reuse (i.e. FAIR data) has found agreement in principle, but it is yet to put in practice at scale. This requires careful consideration of both immediate technical solutions and the future direction of research methodologies and data (re)use.

As defined elsewhere, heritage science encompasses a broad range of disciplines from the arts and the humanities to natural sciences and engineering. Therefore, to make data generated by these separate domains, each with its own professional language and processes, understandable and relevant within the heritage science community, a huge effort needs to be invested into conceptualising and consequently formalising these processes of creating, processing and using heritage science data.

Moreover, beyond technical aspects, there is a crucial social dimension to heritage science data. This involves fostering a sense of community among stakeholders, including institutions and individuals, and addressing their diverse needs and expectations. The social aspect underscores the importance of collaborative efforts and knowledge sharing, which are essential for the sustainable development and effective use of heritage science data.

The building, cohesion and empowerment of the E-RIHS community closely, but also in a broader context of the heritage science community was founded on the strong links developed by the collaborative knowledge co-creation between providers and users in the trans-national access projects on the three E-RIHS physical access platforms / "LABs": ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB. The challenge for E-RIHS now is to extend this pathway digitally, in DIGILAB, which will enable the co-creation of new knowledge through a digital research environment, generating new data or new knowledge by enriching already existing data.

A significant challenge is defining and building the 'scientific matter' for cultural heritage (CH) data scientists. This involves establishing a robust framework for CH data that integrates various scientific disciplines to promote shared protocols and workflows, facilitating interoperability and enhancing the overall quality and accessibility of the data.

It is also crucial to ensure that DIGILAB is perceived as an autonomous entity with specific goals and functions, rather than as an ancillary laboratory. Clear positioning within the existing E-RIHS structure is essential for this.

Furthermore, the development of DIGILAB has historically been challenged by resource constraints, often being treated as an additional initiative rather than a primary focus with dedicated funding. This has impacted its evolution and the speed at which it could respond to these critical needs.

2 UPDATED VERSION OF THE CONCEPTUAL PLAN OF DIGILAB

2.1 From Research Questions to Knowledge Production

DIGILAB's primary ambition is to support the evolution of methodological approaches in the digital transition of various heritage science disciplines. The goal is to promote the production of a new generation of enriched data, transforming it into a valuable, autonomous scientific resource that requires careful curation for scientific and cultural memory.

- **Collaborative Framework and Data Enrichment:** DIGILAB will function as a distributed, adaptable, and open socio-technical system, focusing on knowledge mobilisation rather than mere physical digitisation.
- **Integration with other E-RIHS Labs:** DIGILAB's efforts will complement and enhance those of ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB by integrating digital data culture into all activities and disciplines. This will facilitate seamless data orchestration and reinforce their objectives, making digital data an integral part of heritage science.
- **Autonomy of Digital Cultural Heritage:** DIGILAB will manage digital-born cultural assets and digital representation of tangible and intangible heritage, ensuring their preservation and accessibility. Digital replicas, through semantic enrichment, will be treated as autonomous resources with their own status and specificity.
- **Transdisciplinary Approach:** The methodology involves creating links between heritage objects, actors, scientific activities, and data. This includes data enrichment processes that describe digital assets through metadata and the steps from raw data to interpretation.
- **Reflective Analysis and New Tools:** By developing an open, evolving socio-technical system, DIGILAB will provide an expansive suite of tools for the human-driven collection, categorisation, processing, annotation, interpretation, and visualisation of digital assets. These tools will not only support the management and documentation of existing work but also enable new research opportunities through advanced analytics and machine learning. This approach aims to enhance the autonomous amplification of the data corpus and foster innovative scientific discoveries.
- **Guardian of Digital Memory:** DIGILAB ensures that digital replicas serve as irreplaceable repositories of an object's past, offering historical reference and a foundation for future restorations or reconstructions. Recognising data provenance, tools used, motivations, and methodologies is crucial for effective transdisciplinary research.

By emphasising the journey from research questions to knowledge production, DIGILAB aims at comprehensive documentation of scientific data, thereby facilitating knowledge production and the integration of digital cultural heritage into research.

2.2 Overall Schema

The overall schema for DIGILAB is designed to integrate and enhance the digital dimension of the E-RIHS infrastructure. This schema leverages the collaborative efforts of DIGILAB with ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB to create a comprehensive digital ecosystem.

The schema is based on three foundational aims that will guide the implementation in a short-, mid- and long-term:

- To produce and integrate data representing the complex physical and semantic features of heritage objects from multiple disciplinary perspectives, as generated by E-RIHS-related heritage science processes.
- To ensure the maintenance and accessibility of digital data and processes over time, supporting preservation and re-use of data.
- To build an open and adaptable socio-technical system that evolves with user needs, enabling continuous improvement and service adaptation.
- To actively promote and disseminate digital tools and services that not only support but also conduct Heritage Science research autonomously.

This schema shows how crucial it is to establish robust connections between heritage objects, knowledge objects, and research protocols. The implementation of this schema within the E-RIHS overall strategy will be based on three key elements:

- **Material and Digital Counterparts:** Bridge physical heritage objects and their digital representations, structuring data and related knowledge.
- **Research Protocols:** Combine heritage objects, scientific questions, and instruments within a unified framework.
- **Data Production and Enrichment:** Support the generation, enhancement, and analysis of data across ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB and by connecting existing and future digital tools, services and resources.

As a result of these foundational aims and key elements, DIGILAB will establish a comprehensive knowledge base in heritage science by leveraging data science to facilitate large-scale, cross-disciplinary analyses. This socio-technical platform will integrate heritage objects, actors, scientific activities, and data into a cohesive system, enabling extensive data analysis that reveals new patterns and relationships. By conducting large-scale scenarios, DIGILAB will uncover insights on conservation, restoration, and knowledge dissemination strategies. This approach enhances understanding of heritage data and supports the development of innovative solutions and methodologies in heritage science.

Broadly speaking, the main questions addressed by heritage science are related to the investigation of socio-cultural dimensions of heritage assets (works of art, monuments, etc.), described in terms of, among others, perception, style, aesthetics, etc., description of their materiality, modes of construction (technology of manufacture and techniques of production) and their state of conservation and physical preservation. Thus, there are significant benefits to formalizing the processes of knowledge creation, i.e., moving from observations to statements where inferences are clearly described. This includes providing a formal description of how observations were made (the environmental conditions of the documentation processes, through paradata and metadata) and operating within a new scientific visualization environment that links (semantically-described) data with interpretative statements. DIGILAB could support and enhance these processes, enabling a more efficient and effective approach to scientific inquiry.

Figure 1: Positing DIGILAB in the E-RIHS network.

At the core of the DIGILAB schema (Figure 1) are heritage objects, scientific questions, and instruments representing the primary focus of *research activities*. The arrows illustrate the flow of data and services between DIGILAB, ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB. Digital services (represented by red arrows) support research protocols, while enriched data (represented by blue arrows) enhance the knowledge base. DIGILAB is positioned as the crucial node within this system, facilitating data integration and cross-analysis. It connects digital data back to the core research activities and the broader knowledge base, ensuring a seamless flow of information and enhancing the overall research process.

Through this integrated and dynamic schema, DIGILAB will bridge the physical and digital realms of heritage science, ensuring that data and insights flow efficiently between all components. DIGILAB will also introduce a cohesive environment that enhances the capabilities of ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB, positioning itself as the central hub for digital cultural heritage within the E-RIHS infrastructure. This approach not only ensures the preservation and accessibility of enriched scientific data but also transforms it into a valuable resource for the heritage science community.

3 E-RIHS COMMUNITY WORKSHOPS

3.1 Workshops Objectives

To effectively design DIGILAB within the context of its future user community, a series of workshops were organised. These workshops aimed to foster pragmatic and casual discussions around the experiences of the community in heritage science (HS) from the perspectives of both users and providers of access services. Participants shared first-hand experiences related to data production, analysis, and publication, aligning their insights with the digital services and data workflows.

The workshops focused on understanding the needs and obstacles faced by the community, emphasising collaborative aspects and developing an awareness about data documentation (metadata and paradata), data re-use potential and long-term preservation issues. Each session was organised with key user groups and service providers, drilling down into their existing and future needs. This approach ensured the retention of users by providing valuable insights into the evolving requirements of stakeholders. Participants were selected from the IPERION HS project¹, representing a multidisciplinary blend of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) communities. The criteria included both novice users and experienced users, such as repeat users and trans-platform users. Exemplary providers from each of the three physical platforms (ARCLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB) were also invited on a facultative basis to contribute to the discussions (Table 1).

By engaging these diverse groups, the workshops aimed to align the practical experiences and expectations of the community with the capabilities of DIGILAB, ensuring that the future platform meets the comprehensive needs of its users and service providers.

3.2 Workshops Format

The E-RIHS community workshops were structured to facilitate in-depth discussions and extract valuable insights for the conceptualisation and implementation of DIGILAB. Each workshop was themed around transitioning from existing platforms (ARCLAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB) to DIGILAB through digital data. The format comprised a welcome and introduction session, user presentations, a detailed discussion on data and research processes, and concluding remarks.

Table 1. Workshop overview

Date	2024-02-08 10-12am CET	2024-02-15 10-12am CET	2024-02-22 10-12am CET
Workshop #	Workshop 1 FIXLAB	Workshop 2 ARCLAB	Workshop 3 MOLAB
Workshop title	From FIXLAB to DIGILAB through Digital Data	From ARCLAB to DIGILAB through Digital Data	From MOLAB to DIGILAB through Digital Data
Workshop facilitator	Guillem Anaïs	Guillem Anaïs	Doherty Brenda
Workshop participants	USERS: Ina Reiche, Katarina Muller, Diego Quintero Balbas, Lucrezia Milillo PROVIDER: Marei Hacke	USERS: Romain Thomas, Francesca Gherardi, Marya Albrecht PROVIDERS: Ineke Joosten, Maria Martin Gil	USERS: Thea Winther, Crescenzo Violante, Teresa Palomar PROVIDERS: David Buti, Vincent Detalle

¹ <https://www.iperionhs.eu>

All the workshops followed the same structure in 4 parts:

- **1/Welcome & Introduction:** This welcoming introduction aimed to establish a shared understanding of DIGILAB, its objectives, and the role within E-RIHS and explain the reasons of the workshop. Background slides explained the evolution of E-RIHS and distinguished DIGILAB services from the broader E-RIHS digital infrastructure.
- **2/User Presentations:** Participants shared experiences from three projects, discussing outcomes, impacts, limitations, and areas for improvement. This provided real-world perspectives on current digital services and their enhancements.
- **3/Data and Research Processes Discussion:** this part focused on data production, management, and utilisation. It explored the types of data produced, interactions with data, support mechanisms, and the integration of data into research processes.
- **4/Future Perspectives:** the workshop concluded with a forward-looking discussion on evolving research data needs and potential developments in E-RIHS digital services.

3.3 Results from the Workshops

The workshops yielded valuable insights into various aspects of data management and usage within the heritage science community. Key results are synthesised as follows:

- **Data Nature and Management:** During the workshops, the participants provided detailed descriptions of various data types, including statistical, observational, experimental, textual, and multimedia. The participants highlighted the critical roles these data play in research and how existing services facilitated their management and integration into research processes. It provides concrete use cases for DIGILAB implementation.
- **Objectives and Processes:** Insights were gathered on the specific research goals of participants, the processes of data treatment and transformation, and the importance of documenting these processes. The participants discussed their practices or problems for recording metadata and paradata, as well as the use of controlled vocabularies and thesauri to ensure consistency and accuracy.
- **Challenges and Data Sharing:** The participants identified several obstacles encountered in data usage and sharing, such as issues with data formats, storage, and accessibility. They shared strategies for overcoming these challenges and provided information on their data sharing practices, including the platforms used for storage and whether they employed open or proprietary data formats.
- **Impact on Research:** Concrete examples were provided on how data contributed to addressing research questions and the overall impact of these data on research outcomes. Participants also discussed the transformative effect of data managing on their projects.

By systematically gathering these insights, the workshops aimed to align user experiences with digital service needs, ensuring that DIGILAB is tailored to meet the evolving requirements of the heritage science community. This collaborative approach provided a solid foundation for identifying current and future needs.

4 SURVEY ON EXISTING RESOURCES AND SERVICES THAT COULD SUPPORT E-RIHS DIGILAB INFRASTRUCTURE AND USER NEEDS

4.1 Introduction to the survey

With reference to the conceptual design, digital services and initial pilot infrastructure of DIGILAB as the fourth E-RIHS access platform, and in parallel to the E-RIHS community workshops, an action was focused on collecting information on existing digital resources and services that could be offered by E-RIHS partners.

In this context, we conducted a survey focusing on digital infrastructure, operational services, accessible digital resources, as well as digital services for data processing and re-use, or for cloud collaboration. We started this search and collection of information by surveying the resources available at the national level, in the E-RIHS National Nodes, and by looking at the most pressing challenges at hand.

4.2 Survey Format and Sections

The survey was realised via the <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/> platform. It was structured in five sections.

Introductory part on the institutional profile of the responder

- A. Data Management and Data Access Policy
- B. Digital Infrastructure
- C. Digital Resources for Heritage Science
- D. DIGILAB Digital Services for data analysis, interpretation, enrichment and reuse

4.3 Survey Results

We have collected 26 answers from 10 countries, out of 100 invitations, which are spread among the E-RIHS National Node institutions

Figure 2: Responders from Institutions - members of an E-RIHS National Node.

4.3.A. DATA MANAGEMENT AND DATA ACCESS POLICY

Participants referred to development initiatives of digital platforms that are either fully operational or in progress, which E-RIHS National Nodes are using or participating in the development, namely:

In **Belgium**, BALaT+ is the evolution of the actual BALaT platform (<https://balat.kikirpa.be/>), which will be extended both in data sources and in functionality.

In **France**, the development of a digital platform for E-RIHS.fr is associated with the developments of the ESPADON project (<https://espadon.net/>). ESPADON aims to provide the community with, on one hand, new instrumental means for multi-scale 3D tomographies and 2D multi-physical imaging, made possible notably thanks to the increase in computing power, and, on the other hand, unique digital resources and expertise in multidimensional data processing, management and archiving.

In **Italy**, the Institute of Heritage Science (ISPC) of CNR (leader of the project) and E-RIHS.it (leading European research infrastructure), is engaged in the design and development of the Italian National Node of the E-RIHS DIGILAB platform, which is currently implemented in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience National Programme (PNRR) as part of the Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>).

In **Poland**, a project proposal is being prepared for submission to a national funding programme to develop the DIGITAL E-RIHS.pl platform, and an initiative and discussions are underway to strengthen cooperation with DARIAH.pl, which has developed <https://lab.dariah.pl/en/>.

In **Slovenia**, the following initiatives are of particular interest for E-RIHS.si, both developed by the National and University Library of Slovenia as member and with the support of [Europeana](https://www.europeana.eu/). The Digital Library of Slovenia (<https://www.dlib.si/>), and the national aggregator of e-content (<http://www.agregator.si/>), aimed at maintaining a single point of access and preservation of Slovene e-content from the field of culture.

In **Hungary**, scientific results and findings from archaeological sites are collected in the National Archaeological Repository of the Hungarian National Museum, created as part of the ARIADNE Research Infrastructure AISBL (<https://www.ariadne-research-infrastructure.eu>). Most of the documentation is accessible through the National Archaeology Database (<https://archeodatabase.hnm.hu/en/>).

In the **Netherlands**, the following digital platforms are of particular interest for E-RIHS.nl: the Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) Data Station Archaeology (<https://archaeology.datastations.nl>) and the DCCD portal for dendrochronology (<https://dataverse.nl/dataverse/dccd>). The latter is an initiative of DANS and the Cultural Heritage Agency (RCE), in collaboration with the Netherlands Institute for Art History (RKD), providing access to research databases (<https://research.rkd.nl/en>).

In **Spain**, DIGITAL.CSIC (<https://digital.csic.es>) collects, organizes, and provides open access to a wide variety of research outputs from the Spanish National Research Council. Humanities and Social Sciences is the second most represented research area in the repository, after Natural Resources. The Institute of History is particularly prominent with over 20,000 research outputs. The repository also organizes content from interdisciplinary platforms and hubs, such as Plataforma Temática Interdisciplinar del CSIC Patrimonio Abierto: Investigación y Sociedad (PTI-PAIS) for heritage science and the Red Conexión-Arqueología – Archaeology Hub Archaeology, both relevant to E-RIHS.

The majority of participants responded positively about the use of an established and published Data Management Policy as well as of such a Data Access Policy and provided the URLs in which those documents are accessible.

Table 2. Institutions promoting open access to publications and FAIR data and encouraging the publication of data in open repositories, by countries

Belgium	<p>https://orfeo.belnet.be (publication repository for Belgian federal institutions)</p> <p>https://balat.kikirpa.be (knowledge base/repository for heritage and heritage science datasets)</p> <p>https://closertovaneyck.kikirpa.be (online resource on paintings of Van Eyck)</p>
France	<p>https://www.science-ouverte.cnrs.fr/en/open-research-data-department/</p> <p>https://hal.science/</p>
Hungary	<p>https://archeodatabase.hnm.hu/en (scientific results, along with all results from archaeological sites are collected in the National Archaeological Repository of the Hungarian National Museum. This is a limited access system. HUN-REN ARP https://researchdata.hu/en</p>
Italy	<p>IRIS, Institutional research information system (https://iris.cnr.it/): for publications</p> <p>The Ministry of University and Research has released a "National Plan for Open Science" https://www.mur.gov.it/sites/default/files/2022-06/Piano_Nazionale_per_la_Scienza_Aperta.pdf</p> <p>The RoadMap adopted by CNR towards Open Science is described in: https://zenodo.org/records/7983538#.ZHcC9OxBw6E</p>
The Netherlands	<p>DANS, https://dans.knaw.nl/en/, is the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data; linkeddata.cultureelerfgoed.nl;</p> <p>beeldbank.cultureelerfgoed.nl; catalogus.cultureelerfgoed.nl;</p> <p>The Data Station Archaeology: https://archaeology.datastations.nl</p> <p>DataverseNL: a research data repository co-provided by DANS and participating institutions: https://dataverse.nl</p>
Poland	<p>https://repod.icm.edu.pl/dataverse/umk (Repository of research data)</p> <p>https://repozytorium.umk.pl/ (Repository of full texts (RUMAK))</p> <p>https://www.bg.pw.edu.pl/index.php/en/</p>
Romania	<p>https://infraart.inoe.ro/</p> <p>https://certo.inoe.ro/implement_ppta/</p> <p>https://certo.inoe.ro/test/published-work/</p> <p>https://gorjan-brancusi.inoe.ro/</p>
Slovenia	<p>https://dk.um.si/info/index.php/eng/introduction</p> <p>Open Source on Digital library of Slovenia (https://www.dlib.si/)</p>
Spain	<p>https://rodin.uca.es/</p> <p>https://digital.csic.es</p> <p>CSIC Open Access Mandate (available at Mandato Institucional de Acceso Abierto DIGITAL.CSIC) requires institutional researchers to deposit their underlying datasets in DIGITAL.CSIC repository upon publication of associated articles/books/other peer reviewed works. DIGITAL.CSIC has an own tool to estimate the level of FAIRness (FAIR EVA https://fair.csic.es/es), which is based on RDA Data Maturity indicators. Compliance of mandate requirements are published at the https://digital.csic.es/sites/monitor_mandato_oa_csic/ and level of compliance is a factor in annual institutional a scientific assessment exercise. Also, different CSIC communities take part in several EOSC related initiatives such as EPOS, DARIAH/CLARIN, LifeWatch. CSIC community participating in EPOS infrastructure use DIGITAL.CSIC to contribute with research data (for the time being). In the future they will also use the repository to provide research software and publications to EPOS.</p>

4.3.B. DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

For institutions deploying infrastructure of a portal or services for hosting, managing and maintaining data repositories, there are several solutions adopted, at institutional or national level. For the institutions hosting or having access to a cloud-based research data repository, among the reported software solutions adopted were Owncloud (3), Nextcloud (2), Dataverse (2), PioneerBox (1), Azurecloud (1), ODC-Noord, ABS (1), DSPACE-CRIS (1).

Figure 3: Solutions adopted, at institutional or national level for hosting, managing and maintaining data repositories.

Most of the reported data repositories offer services of (a) Data sharing, access and re-use; (b) Data documentation (metadata provision, integration); (c) Data storage and retrieval: data indexing and data archiving/integration; while a few of them are offering advanced services such as Semantic representation and mapping , advanced search methods & techniques (advanced open-source, semantic search engines) or data FAIRification services.

In response to the question of whether institutions would be able to provide and support the necessary infrastructure for a virtual collaborative research environment and services for the collaborative building of HS knowledge in E-RIHS-ERIC, a number of solutions under development were mentioned, as follows,

- CNR (ISPC, IMATI) institutions are developing Collaborative Virtual Research Environment services to be implemented in E-RIHS.DIGILAB.it where researchers will be able to define their own research workflow from scratch or from selecting existing workflows in a shared library, and then (optionally) run it in the VRE.
- University Library of Maribor University is involved in ongoing project building the Slovenian Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (SCCCH) parallel to the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH).
- RKD Netherlands Institute for Art History is in an early phase of development to incorporate HS in their research network of art historical data.
- Since 2019, CNRS and other partners are developing a digital platform for the centralization and long-term preservation of multidisciplinary scientific data by integrating research tools designed for (or adapted to) stakeholders involved in the Notre Dame science project. This toolkit supports functions such as data ingestion (Esmeralda), content indexing (ArcheoGRID), thesaurus structuring (Opentheso), interactive 3D exploration of archaeological remains (3DHOP), image-based 3D annotation of architectural scenes (Aioli) and multimodal exploration of the cathedral-scale data

corpus (NDP 3D Viewer). This platform is today used as model by Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine (FSP) for building the future ESPADON digital services for the French heritage science community.

- UK is currently investing substantial resources in the development of UK heritage digital infrastructure <https://www.heritagescienceforum.org.uk/what-we-do/riches>.

4.3.C. DIGITAL RESOURCES FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

All institutions that participated in the survey have relevant data and learning/working resources to contribute to the E-RIHS knowledge base, such as scientific datasets (research data, spectra, graphs, colour measurements); technical/scientific images; 3D models of heritage/art objects; historical audiovisual archival documents (photographs, films, audios); literature textual resources (research papers, historical text resources, scientific literature, technical reports); standards, protocols, policies; reference materials or other resources; vocabulary services, glossaries, common vocabularies; open-source research tools for specific applications (such as preventive conservation digital tools); guidelines, tutorials, best practices, methodologies, workflows; training material/educational resources. These resources are presented in numbers in the figure.

Figure 4: Types of digital resources that are available for educational or working applications.

4.3.D. DIGITAL SERVICES FOR DATA ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION, ENRICHMENT AND REUSE

Existing tools were mentioned in relation to the following services for data analysis, interpretation, enrichment and re-use:

Figure 5: Existing tools were mentioned in relation to the following services for data analysis, interpretation, enrichment and re-use.

Among the digital resources or services that are intended to be offered in E-RIHS DIGILAB, participants mentioned the following categories:

Figure 6: Digital resources or services that are intended to be offered in DIGILAB by E-RIHS National Nodes.

5 IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

5.1 DIGILAB in the Future European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage

DIGILAB will play a pivotal role within the European landscape of digital transition in science and cultural heritage, particularly through its involvement in European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science (ECHOES), the recently launched EU-funded initiative with the ambitious role to establish and implement the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). Among others, ECHOES aims at establishing a digital platform that facilitates collaboration among cultural heritage communities involved in the research, management, conservation and valorisation of heritage. ECHOES addresses the need for preserving and digitally accessing cultural heritage data, by leveraging the digital revolution to enhance data acquisition, analysis, and sharing. With the ambition to shift from an object-focused approach to a holistic digital transformation, ECHOES encompasses both tangible and intangible heritage assets. Its objectives include preserving cultural heritage for future generations, making it digitally accessible, and fostering collaboration to overcome the digital divide and fragmented data issues. The project adheres to Open Science and FAIR data principles, envisioning a Digital Commons where actors can collaboratively construct interpretations and contribute to knowledge through elements like digital twins, a digital ecosystem, and a digital *continuum*, ensuring interoperability and traceability of heritage data. Ultimately, ECHOES aims at triggering a paradigm shift in cultural heritage, transforming the discipline from a competitive one to a collaborative one, building a community working together towards creating digital commons, built around the concept of semantic-aware heritage digital twins, enriched and continuously updated with multi-disciplinary data and related information. Consequently, ECHOES must ensure the re-use of digital twins in various scenarios, by ensuring their digital *continuum*.

There are several aspects in the expected outcomes of the ECHOES project that are in line with the objectives of the DIGILAB implementation plan, such as to foster the management and accessibility of cultural heritage data through the creation of collaborative digital platforms; to focus on centralising, curating, and making accessible vast amounts of data on heritage science, leveraging advanced technologies like knowledge graphs, visualisation tools, and artificial intelligence to enhance data analysis and management. However, there are distinct differences in their approaches and goals that suggest complementary roles within the European heritage community as it embraces the digital transition.

ECHOES employs a modular approach, integrating a broad network of parallel projects, including cascading grants and specific vertical applications. This flexibility facilitates the development and integration of new applications and tools by the heritage community, promoting innovation and adaptability. Additionally, ECHOES emphasises sustainability by creating a long-term legal entity to manage the collaborative platform, ensuring its viability and continuous evolution.

Complementarily, DIGILAB focuses specifically on managing the data lifecycle within heritage science. It aims to create a collaborative virtual research environment that works in close integration with existing infrastructures like ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB. By progressively structuring research protocols, workflows and methods into a cumulative knowledge base, DIGILAB aspires to become a reference point for data related to the conservation and valorisation of cultural heritage in Europe.

The articulation between ECHOES and DIGILAB lies in their complementary strengths. ECHOES can benefit from DIGILAB's structured approach to data lifecycle management and its integration with established infrastructures, enhancing the depth and reliability of the collaborative platform. Conversely, DIGILAB can leverage the innovative and flexible environment of ECHOES to integrate new applications and tools, ensuring its knowledge base remains cutting-edge and comprehensive. Together, they form a cohesive framework that advances the digital transition in heritage science, fostering a robust, sustainable, and innovative digital ecosystem for cultural heritage in Europe.

5.2 DIGILAB and the European Open Science Cloud

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) aims to be built on top of resources and services from a wide range of national, regional and institutional infrastructures throughout Europe. Indeed, the report “A landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework – Capabilities and Gaps” (2023, <https://zenodo.org/records/8399710>) by the EOSC – A Task Force on “Technical Interoperability of Data and Services” collects the most up-to-date information regarding the EOSC Interoperability Framework, its main capabilities and implementation status. The report emphasises the importance of securing a convergence towards a common idea of what the EOSC Interoperability Framework should be.

The concept of “System of Systems” is the core basis of EOSC and therefore the EOSC – A Task Force on “Technical Interoperability of Data and Services” proposes a unique framework for ESRIs, thematic clusters, general purpose infrastructures and cross domain initiatives to have an active role in this endeavour. National initiatives fall under this varied and vibrant ecosystem and are the result of yearlong efforts promoted and funded by national data and open science policies and strategies. A major challenge is to transform such initiatives in transnational services within EOSC. Our present report (section 4) gives an overview of existing infrastructures of resources and services in E-RIHS IP countries that could support DIGILAB infrastructure and user needs.

There are technical, legal, and policy considerations to take into account to prepare the grounds for a coordination amongst such national initiatives and enable their active participation in EOSC through DIGILAB infrastructure. In this regard, work by previous EOSC efforts such as EOSC Pillar project (<https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/eosc-pillar-national-initiatives-transnational-services>) can be useful to identify main issues at stake: for instance, identify and highlight common policies and approaches at national levels; highlight critical issues in the legal and policy framework of the countries that can hamper collaboration and interoperability, and suggest means to address these challenges; explore cross-country federation opportunities and procedures; and define common tools and frameworks to describe, enrol, and support national service/data providers are not to be neglected.

These considerations are to be developed under the EOSC Interoperability Framework and its recommendations about the APIs, the metadata format of the exchanged data and all the processes required to really make EOSC resources interoperable. Practical experience from other discipline communities participating in EOSC and already at an advanced stage in the building of their digital infrastructures of services and data can be useful models for E-RIHS community of national infrastructures and DIGILAB. In this regard, the experience, regulations and recommendations from European Plate Observing System (EPOS) for earth science community of national research infrastructures (<https://www.epos-eu.org/about-epos/what-we-do>) and from European Life-Science Infrastructure (ELIXIR) for life sciences national communities (<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/how-countries-join>) can be highlighting.

Commons issues in the coordination of existing national initiatives of digital infrastructures of data and services for their active participation in DIGILAB construction may include:

1. A detailed overview of metadata schemas, formats, controlled vocabularies, open interoperability protocols and other technological standards, access policies and mechanisms, digital security policies and legal frameworks and provisions that regulate the technological architecture of the national initiatives. Governance and funding policies are also important to consider so as to secure long-term participation and sustainability.
2. Based on findings and analysis of point 1, work on a collaboration agreement with DIGILAB that identifies and lists all services and data collections to be contributed. Each national node adopts its own process for selecting their nominated services. Compliance and commitment with DIGILAB open science, legal, ethical and social implications policy are included in this agreement.
3. A workplan to support a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary data management plan that facilitates the building and growth of a DIGILAB community through shared access policies and rules.
4. Compliance with all relevant European and International legislation on data and IPR protection.

5.3 DIGILAB Implementation Layers

The implementation of DIGILAB will be realised through a structured approach, addressing four distinct layers, each with specific goals and strategies:

- **Layer 0: Community Building and Initial Digital Services Identification.** This foundational layer focuses on creating a cohesive and collaborative community within E-RIHS, ensuring active engagement and participation from all stakeholders.
- **Layer 1: Managing the Data Lifecycle.** This layer aims at establishing a robust infrastructure that interlinks various digital tools and services, facilitating seamless integration and interoperability across the E-RIHS network.
- **Layer 2: Towards an Integrated Virtual Research Environment.** The goal here is to develop a comprehensive virtual research environment that supports advanced research capabilities, including visualisation, annotation, and documentation.
- **Layer 3: Towards a Heritage Science Knowledge Base.** This ultimate layer involves creating a rich, interconnected knowledge base that consolidates data and insights from heritage science research, enabling advanced data analysis and knowledge discovery.

In the following sections each layer will be presented through a detailed methodology.

- **Description of Socio-Technical Challenges:** Each layer will begin with an explanation of the socio-technical challenges that need to be addressed. This includes understanding the specific requirements of the community, the existing gaps, and the broader context in which these layers will operate.
- **Identification of Key Needs:** Key needs for each layer will be identified, outlining the essential tools, services, and capabilities required to achieve the layer's objectives. This involves detailing the specific functionalities and integrations necessary for effective implementation.
- **Confrontation with Community Survey Results:** The identified key needs will be compared with the results of surveys conducted within the E-RIHS community. This comparison will help associate each need with existing tools and services, pinpoint the starting points, and recognise ongoing projects that will yield usable results in the coming years. This step ensures that the strategy is grounded in the current landscape of digital tools and services.
- **Strategy for Implementation:** For each layer, the strategy will be described in terms of documenting the existing tools and services that can serve as the foundation for further development, highlighting tools and services that are currently under development (e.g., in ECCCH or "national nodes level" initiatives) and will be integrated into the strategy, and identifying the gaps that remain and outlining the steps needed to plan and implement new tools and services at the E-RIHS level.

This method allows for a comprehensive implementation strategy that is adequately granular, aligning with the scale of implementation. It will harmonise European-wide initiatives with projects occurring at different levels, including research organisations, collaborative projects, and national aggregations. Each identified need will be assessed based on priority and the maturity level of available services (or initial reflexion on formalisation topics). This strategy, which is presented here as an initial methodological result, will underpin

the first phases of DIGILAB's implementation (Layer 0). Indeed, this framework of needs and available solutions can serve as an initial scaffold to map the resources within the community and identify the primary stakeholders of DIGILAB.

LAYER 0. DIGILAB COMMUNITY BUILDING AND INITIAL DIGITAL SERVICES IDENTIFICATION

Based on the workshops organised during this E-RIHS Implementation Phase (IP) project, inclusive engagement measures must be taken by involving potential users and service providers through regular meetings and workshops to understand their needs, gather feedback, and ensure their active participation. Collaborative platforms should be designed (and developed) to allow seamless interaction between users and service providers, promoting the exchange of ideas and the co-creation of solutions (from the scale of a service to the scale of a lab). In most cases, the available interaction time between the facility/service provider and the user is limited and is entirely devoted to performing the measurements as well as possible and obtaining as many results as possible from the heritage object. There is rarely time for collaboration in the processing and interpretation of results. The creation of a digital virtual research environment where provider and user will continue to collaborate in processing the results with appropriate specialised software tools is the appropriate framework for extending the time and opportunities for collaboration and co-creation on the given project. Additionally, normalisation of practices is crucial; establishing normalised protocols and workflows for data creation, processing and management will ensure consistency and interoperability across different labs and projects. Capacity building through training and support for users and service providers will enhance their capabilities in utilising the digital services and tools effectively. Furthermore, it is essential to raise awareness among users to identify the role of digital data from the early phases of their research project design. This includes understanding its direct use in the project and its potential for reuse and interconnection with other data. The goal is to make the production of FAIR data a scientific priority (and a large-scale data analysis perspective), rather than merely a compliance requirement. Another crucial aspect relates to the ability of assessing quality of data by the various communities of use, in terms of enabling tracing the provenance of this data and its full transparency (technical, i.e. formats) and conceptual (semantics).

Key needs for Community Building and Initial Digital Services Identification (KN_Ax)

To effectively support the E-RIHS community and facilitate seamless access to resources, a robust framework for identifying digital services, managing users and access is essential. This involves implementing several key services and tools to foster community building and ensure secure and unified access to digital resources.

- **KN_A1. Community Integration and Collaboration** – Develop a web platform to facilitate interactions, community building, and collaboration among E-RIHS members.
- **KN_A2. Virtual and Specialised Communication** – Provide tools for organising virtual events and specialised communication channels to support structured discourse and knowledge sharing within the community.
- **KN_A3. Unified Access and Authentication** – Implement a dedicated authentication system (by using already existing authentication framework from the E-RIHS partners) for unified access to all E-RIHS resources.
- **KN_A4. Identifying and Gathering Initial Digital Services** – Implement a collaborative service for continuously gathering information on digital services.

Table 3. Layer 0: Key needs for community building (KN_Ax)

KEY NEEDS	TOOLS AND SERVICES		
	Existing (or starting point)	Already planned	To plan/implement
KN_A1 Community Integration and Collaboration	Software solutions for managing social networking, already experimented in research projects		A dedicated Forum, by using https://e-rihs.io as a starting point (organize online workshops and webinars to introduce and demonstrate the forum; develop a best practices guide for effective communication and collaboration; establish a feedback mechanism to gather user input and improve the platform).
KN_A2 Virtual and Specialized Communication	Platforms for Visio conferencing Web channels for archiving virtual events		Integrate Platforms for Visio conferencing and Web channels for archiving virtual events (develop a centralized scheduling and management system; implement a comprehensive archiving solution with metadata tagging; establish partnerships with existing conferencing platforms for tailored solutions).
KN_A3 Unified Access and Authentication	Several solutions already deployed at national level (or EU project level) ORCID OAuth2 as a single-sign-on service		A dedicated platform for social networking; develop a centralised user management system;
KN_A4 Identifying and Gathering Initial Digital Services	First survey done		Dedicated workshops for identifying and integrating existing and future digital services (organize thematic workshops with key stakeholders to map existing digital services and identify gaps; develop a collaborative digital catalog for existing services, tools, and datasets; establish a task force to monitor and evaluate new digital services for integration into DIGILAB).

LAYER 1. MANAGING THE DATA LIFECYCLE

This layer refers to a socio-technical strategy aiming at supporting the E-RIHS community for a data lifecycle management in a set of distributed services across E-RIHS members, interconnected by a common strategy for data referencing and activity documentation.

This strategy must focus on creating a context where semantically rich data is produced, capable of integrating fundamental links between heritage assets, research questions, protocols, instruments, and human skills belonging to various services. By establishing these connections, the foundation for constructing a collective knowledge base can be laid (see layer 3).

Given the dispersion and heterogeneity of tools and services, metadata and paradata schemas, and vocabularies, it is necessary to highlight the need for experimenting with an interoperability framework for the entire data lifecycle tailored to the specificities of representative thematic areas (or projects typologies).

This experimentation should start with a few pilot projects, especially within a highly multidisciplinary context, to promote multi-scalar interoperability measures using a bottom-up approach rather than a prescriptive top-down method. The aim is to promote the replicability of a collaborative experience model (linked to a research project) where data structuring, documentation, conservation become an opportunity (including for service providers) and add a natural scientific value to the project, rather than a constraint.

There has been an ongoing effort in E-RIHS IP, a synergy action stemming from a specific task in IPERION HS, T6.3, to improve the interoperability of processes and data produced across E-RIHS access platforms, taking into account the entire user journey and data lifecycle, from the formulation of research questions and the design of a research project, through the application and realisation of the access project, to the dissemination of results and their contribution to the heritage science knowledge (Gibson et al., 2023) (Padfield et al., 2022). This effort started with a limited scope, dealing with a short list of selected cases, but has been progressively extended to provide a more generic approach to achieve interoperability, proposing a versatile modular data model and practical solutions for metadata capture for documentation and overall management of data as they flow through the access channels. The results of the ongoing work will be shared in a GitHub group space, <https://github.com/E-RIHS/hs-interoperability>. In this joint activity, a prioritised goal was the validation of the proposed modelling approach in the E-RIHS dataflow, testing representative workflows at a pilot stage to demonstrate efficiency in data management and ensure FAIRness of datasets.

Figure 7: Focus on the metadata/paradata and data lifecycle in the conceptual schema.

Key needs for Data Lifecycle Management (KN_Bx)

To support the comprehensive management of data throughout its lifecycle, DIGILAB must implement advanced tools and services designed to facilitate data ingestion, storage, curation, contextualisation, and long-term preservation for research stakeholders.

- **KN_B1 Data Ingestion and Normalisation** – User-friendly web interface for secure data deposit, FAIR management and publication, with automated processes for metadata normalisation and visual aids for enhanced data interaction.
- **KN_B2 Data Storage, Organisation, and Retrieval** – A dedicated repository for data storage with semi-automated organisation and robust validation processes for long-term data integrity.
- **KN_B3 Long-Term Digital Data Preservation** – Strategies for long-term preservation of digital content, including format conversions and collaboration with archival institutions to ensure data validity and readability.
- **KN_B4 Contextual Data Acquisition** – Pair data with metadata and paradata throughout the project lifecycle to ensure contextualised and enriched data from the outset.

Table 4. Layer 1: Key needs for managing the data cycle (KN_Bx)

NEEDS	TOOLS AND SERVICES		
	Existing (or starting points)	Already planned	To plan / implement
KN_B1 Data Ingestion and Normalization	DIGITAL.CSIC HumaNum (CNRS) ISPC Dataspace HESCIDA/DIGILAB.be	DIGILAB.it Heritage Data Integration module (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Design a federated metadata normalization processes for ensuring compatibility with E-RIHS digilab framework
KN_B2 Data Storage, Organization, and Retrieval	Archeovision collaborative platform ArcheoGRID DIGITAL.CSIC ISPC Dataspace HESCIDA/DIGILAB.be	DIGILAB.it Heritage Data Integration module (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	A federated E-RIHS PID service (utilise the work already done with handle.net; establish decentralised PID nodes across national and institutional repositories for consistent referencing and retrieval). Enhance existing storage solutions with a federated approach (extend capabilities of existing platforms to support decentralised data storage and organisation)
KN_B3 Long-Term Digital Data Preservation	CINES DIGITAL.CSIC HESCIDA/H-SEARCH	DIGILAB.it: Data processing and curation module (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Design a decentralised preservation repository network
KN_B4 Contextual Data Acquisition	Experimental tools: Memos (FSP-CNRS), OpenAire Broker in DIGITAL.CSIC - to manage suggestions for semantic enrichments of research outputs		Design a framework for contextual data acquisition using federated systems

Key needs for Data Indexing and Semantic Enrichment (KN_Cx)

To meet the diverse data types, uses, and research requirements within the E-RIHS community, robust tools and services for data indexing and semantic enrichment are essential.

- **KN_C1 Comprehensive Data Selection and Indexing** – Build systems to accommodate various data types, with custom metadata schemas, guided processes for data categorisation.
- **KN_C2 Data Corpora Exploration and Integration** – Provide a web-based platform for collaborative categorisation and documentation of multimedia assets, ensuring data interoperability and usability (possibly through accessible APIs).
- **KN_C3 Controlled Vocabulary Management** – Implement a thesaurus management system to synchronise and collaboratively curate multidisciplinary vocabularies, ensuring consistency, interoperability, and transparency in terminology use.

Table 5. Layer 1: key needs for the data indexing and enrichment (KN_Cx)

NEEDS	TOOLS AND SERVICES		
	Existing (or starting point)	Already Planned	To plan/implement
KN_C1 Comprehensive Data Selection and Indexing	Existing tools already used in HS projects: Synthesis, ArcheoGRID	DIGILAB.it (DIGILAB-Data Infrastructure module) (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Design/deploy federated indexing services (allow decentralised indexing across repositories by ensuring interoperability and seamless integration of data from diverse sources).
KN_C2 Data Corpora Exploration and Integration	Extended Matrix	DIGILAB.it (Semantic Data module) (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Plan to connect DIGITAL.CSIC with Jupyter Notebook Promote a federated approach to data exploration; enable cross-repository search and retrieval capabilities.
KN_C3 Controlled Vocabulary Management	Existing tools already used in HS projects (e.g. THEMAS, OPENTHESO, ...) API Integration of UNESCO AGROVOC and SDG vocabularies in DIGITAL.CSIC deposit form Enrichment of DIGITAL.CSIC outputs with JEL, DDC, arXiv controlled vocabularies through OpenAire Broker	DIGILAB.it (Semantic Resources Manager module) (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Develop and deploy vocab.e-rihs.io as the central vocabulary service for E-RIHS (build on the existing prototype based on Opentheso). Establish a decentralised vocabulary management framework (allow contributions and updates from multiple national and institutional repositories; ensure consistency and interoperability of controlled vocabularies across the E-RIHS network). Design and Implement continuous enrichment processes to support multilingual and cross-disciplinary vocabularies to cater to diverse research needs.

LAYER 2. TOWARDS AN INTEGRATED VIRTUAL RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT

Building a Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for the E-RIHS community is the most advanced challenge to address at the socio-technical level because it concerns the effective interaction between DIGILAB and the platforms ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB through digital data production and collaborative use. This environment must facilitate advanced capabilities for visualisation, annotation, and comprehensive documentation, ensuring a robust connection between heritage objects and the extensive datasets and information related to their digitisation. By articulating services at the provider level and ensuring robust links at the DIGILAB level, a cohesive and efficient VRE can be established, supporting rigorous research and collaboration.

Additionally, there is a need to create an interoperability framework for describing material objects, the scientific activities conducted on these objects, and the enrichment and usage of their multiple digital representations. This framework will ensure traceability of activities conducted by multiple actors under common denominators, aiming to foster collaborative research and the construction of shared scientific resources.

As with the implementation strategy described for data lifecycle management (Layer 1), it will be necessary to explore these challenges initially through a few pilot projects. These projects can become models of reproducible collaborative experiences. It is important not to view the construction of a VRE as merely the addition of available digital tools or services, but to involve the designers and developers of these software solutions within the research project. This involvement ensures that scientific challenges can drive the evolution of these tools, adapting them to the specific issues of the context.

Figure 8: Focus on the digital services in the conceptual schema.

Key Needs for Virtual Research Environment (KN_Dx)

To create an effective Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for the E-RIHS community, several advanced capabilities and integrations are necessary. These include visualisation and annotation tools, comprehensive documentation links between physical and digital objects, and robust systems for managing paradata and digital twins.

- **KN_D1 Advanced Visualisation and Annotation** – Support high-resolution visualisation and annotation for multimedia documentation, enhancing detailed analysis and understanding of heritage objects.
- **KN_D2 Integration of Physical and Digital Information** – Create robust links between physical objects and their digital counterparts, ensuring comprehensive documentation and unified access to all relevant data.
- **KN_D3 Lifecycle Paradata and Provenance Management** – Maintain detailed records of digital asset lifecycles and scientific record provenance, using structured metadata to support rigorous research tracking.
- **KN_D4 Digital Twins and Continuum Management** – Develop dynamic digital replicas (digital twins) and a digital *continuum* for seamless data management and use, supporting collaborative CRUD operations and multimodal visualisations.

Table 6. Layer 2: Key needs for Virtual Research Environment (KN_Dx)

NEEDS	TOOLS AND SERVICES		
	Existing (or starting points)	Already planned	To plan / implement
<p>KN_D1</p> <p>Advanced Visualization and Annotation</p>	<p>Software libraries for 2D and 3D data visualisation, also including web-based technologies e.g., IIF, Nexus (CNR), Timelapse thermography 3D viewer (..)</p> <p>Tools for managing and authoring 3D content, e.g., 3D-HOP (CNR), ATON (CNR), ...</p> <p>Tools for 3D annotation, e.g., 3D HOP (CNR), 3D ANNOTATION tool, Aioli (CNRS), ...</p> <p>Tools for shape analysis, e.g., GRAVIFIX tool (CNR), SimilarityLib (CNR), ...</p> <p>Open Peer Review Module integrated in DIGITALCSIC to conduct open peer reviews and open annotations on the repository's outputs.</p>	<p>DIGILAB.it (E-RIHS@H2IOSC) is already developing several pilot projects to demonstrate multiple way of visualisation and annotation:</p> <p>- Illuminated manuscript pilot uses the 3D digital twin of the manuscript to collect all semantic data/paradata related to the item (historical, artistical, diagnostic, etc.) giving also the chance of online annotation</p> <p>- Heriverse let the user navigate in a 3D environment generated on the basis of the Extended Matrix description expressed and stored in a knowledge graph form</p>	<p>Expand the use of existing software libraries for 2D and 3D data visualisation and annotation ;</p> <p>Design an interoperability framework for managing several the visualisation, annotation and analysis scenarios of 2D and 3D representations</p> <p>Develop a centralised repository for visualisation tools;</p> <p>Promote the experimentation (e.g. pilots projects) of these tools across the E-RIHS community for collaborative study of digitised content.</p>

<p>KN_D2 Integration of Physical and Digital Information</p>	<p>ATON (CNR)</p>	<p>AR/MR module for Aioli (CNRS) DIGILAB.it (pilots projects: Illuminated Manuscripts and Heriverse) (E-RIHS@H2IOSC) Spatial hEritage scieNce oNline Sensor Environment (SENNSE) will provide 3D Virtual Navigation and AR features. (E-RISH@H2IOSC)</p>	<p>Develop pilot projects for integrating experimenting with physical and digital data; create detailed documentation and best practices guides based on these pilots;</p>
<p>KN_D3 Lifecycle Paradata and Provenance Management</p>	<p>Extended Matrix (CNR)</p>		<p>Potential solutions coming from HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01-03 (Innovative tools for advanced data enrichment) and HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01-02 (Innovative tools for documenting, interlinking and organising data)</p>
<p>KN_D4 Digital Twins and Continuum Management</p>			<p>Potential solutions coming from HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01-05 (Innovative tools for the study, conservation and restoration of heritage objects)</p>

LAYER 3. TOWARDS A E-RIHS KNOWLEDGE BASE

The E-RIHS knowledge base is the long-term goal of DIGILAB, but it can benefit from the early contributions made during the initial phases of DIGILAB’s design. The primary objective is to gather information from the research projects conducted by the E-RIHS community, aiming to “track, memorize, and correlate” the key elements of research protocols employed by researchers. This involves the intersection of research questions, heritage objects, and study protocols. The knowledge base will be instrumental in mapping the community’s diverse facets—disciplinary, instrumental, and methodological—highlighting the richness and complementarity of perspectives on complex heritage objects. This interconnected database will serve as a co-production framework for representing collective intelligence. By leveraging AI’s potential for analysis, classification, and generation, this knowledge base will enable large-scale data analysis and correlation scenarios,

amplifying the utility and impact of accumulated knowledge. The first steps will involve creating an initial conceptual skeleton of the knowledge domain to be represented. This will be achieved by extracting salient elements from the realms of material objects and knowledge objects from the research reports of projects conducted within E-RIHS, starting from its early prefiguration and implementation phases. The first steps done in this direction are integrated into the The E-RIHS knowledge base (<https://e-rihs.io>) a first repository of information about the E-RIHS infrastructure, services, and resources. It is designed to support the E-RIHS community in sharing and discovering information about the E-RIHS infrastructure, services, and resources. Currently, the knowledge base is powered by Cordra, a platform for building and managing digital objects.

Figure 9: Focus on the knowledge base in the conceptual schema.

Key needs for Research Workflow Design (KN_Ex)

To facilitate efficient and structured research processes within the E-RIHS community, a user-friendly web interface for designing research workflows is essential. This interface allows researchers to design a research process composed of a sequence of steps, each decorated with properties that describe the specific activities involved.

KN_E1 Structured Workflow and Resource Models – Design a user-friendly interface for creating research workflows, enriching each step with properties that define relevant resource models and ensuring accurate activity contextualisation.

KN_E2 Semantic Mapping for Interoperability – Map workflow properties to a common data model (e.g., CIDOC CRM) to facilitate seamless integration and understanding across different research domains.

KN_E3 Automated and Manual Workflow Population – Enable users to populate workflow steps manually or automatically by parsing existing data files to streamline the process and reduce manual effort.

Table 7. Layer 3: Key needs for research workflow design (KN_Ex)

NEEDS	TOOLS AND SERVICES		
	Existing (or starting points)	Already planned	To plan / implement
KN_E1 Structured Workflow and Resource Models	Simplified dataset focused model: https://research.ng-london.org.uk/modelling/?url=https%3A%2F%2Fraw.githubusercontent.com%2FE-RIHS%2Fhs-interoperability%2Fmain%2FDMP%2FIPERION-HS+DMP+Simplified+Workflow+V1.2.tsv Experimental software (Synthesis, Memoria, ...)	DIGILAB.it (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Develop a centralised repository for workflow templates (aggregate templates from various projects and make them easily accessible within DIGILAB; Promote the use of standardised templates across the community.
KN_E2 Semantic Mapping for Interoperability	The X3ML Toolkit OntoRefine	DIGILAB.it (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Design a federated and cumulative approach to semantic mapping (dedicated to the E-RIHS community)
KN_E3 Automated and Manual Workflow Population	DIGITAL.CSIC has both options, manual deposit via DSpace CRIS submission form, semiautomated process through integration with institutional CRIS and automated population through connection with external content providers APIs (ORCID, arXiv, Scopus..)	METAREVE (FSP) DIGILAB.it (E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Design a federated approach to workflow population (e.g. a dedicated service for extracting workflow signatures from project's reports)

Key Needs for Data analysis and Knowledge Discovery

To support advanced knowledge discovery within the E-RIHS community, a web-based customisable interface is essential. This interface should be capable of representing data in multiple modalities to accommodate various research needs and preferences.

- **KN_F1 Multimodal and Dynamic Data Representation** – Implement flexible data viewports and dynamic generation of appropriate data representations based on research questions and user profiles.
- **KN_F2 Multi-Dimensional Visualisation and Knowledge Graphs** – Enable multi-dimensional data visualisation and knowledge graph representation to explore complex relationships and maintain semantic data connections.

- **KN_F3 Comprehensive Search Engine Integration** – Provide a powerful search engine to access comprehensive search results from both internal and external data sources, enhancing knowledge discovery.

Table 8. Layer 3: key needs for data analysis and Knowledge discovery (KN_Fx)

NEEDS	TOOLS AND SERVICES		
	Existing (or starting points)	Already Planned	To plan / implement
KN_F1 Multimodal and Dynamic Data Representation	Knowledge bases on material degradation/preventive conservation (e.g. AGATO, GETAPAR, HERIe)	CLIMPACTH DIGILAB.it E-RIHS@H2IOSC)	Design an integration strategy for gathering existing knowledge bases on material degradation and preventive conservation
KN_F2 Multi-Dimensional Visualisation and Knowledge Graphs	Viewer NDP	DIGILAB.it (E-RIHS@H2IOSC) DIGILAB.it natively provides the exploration of the knowledge base using a semantic knowledge graph. To improve the UX, DIGILAB.it will implement filters based on the semantic properties to limit the number of visualized nodes.	
KN_F3 Comprehensive Search Engine Integration		DIGILAB.it (E-RIHS@H2IOSC) Considering that the DIGILAB.it data model is semantic and based on CIDOC-CRM, DIGILAB.it will implement a powerful tool to search data and metadata in the internal repositories, in the harvested data sources, and the external linked repositories.	

DATA ANALYSIS PERSPECTIVES, IA AND ETHICS

On the basis of current and future research works, more perspective key needs related to the knowledge base layer concern:

- **Advanced Environments for Knowledge Discovery** - Provide an environment to trace inferences and scientific statements, to reconstruct reasoning processes involved in the data-cycle processes - Enable the diachronic analysis and integration of data related to same heritage asset, obtained through different processes, sensors and software.
- **AI-Based Data & Knowledge Processing** – The quick evolution of AI models with deep and machine learning spreads the use of AI and already impacts digital-native data. It is yet too recent that the impact

on the CH/HS field is still to be assessed. The AI is expected to become a key component in the data workflow, digital services, etc.

Bender and colleagues (Bender et al., 2021) offer a very coherent overview on the risks related to Large Language Models (LLM) and AI. The current trend of building always bigger AI-models and ever bigger training datasets have real environmental and social impacts. In a nutshell, the current benchmark of the cost for model training and development is calculated in \$ and Co2 emissions, while we should be considering the cost vs their accuracy gains. Regarding the social impact, they show how LLMs encode biases that can be hurtful for marginalised communities. Since the communities of CH and HS are rallied around the study of human cultures and interdisciplinary, an ethical use of AI should be a priority. In the implementation of E-RIHS, a committee dedicated to the ethical use of AI, composed with external members, will be established. This committee will be consulted for the strategic choices to be made for the implementation.

5.4 Tentative Timeline

The following tentative timeline is conditioned upon financial support opportunities related to the development of E-RIHS, the EU project calls related to digital spheres in cultural heritage, particularly those associated with the ECCCH program, as well as the evolving interaction between initiatives led by E-RIHS members at national levels. The implementation plan would greatly benefit from funding for a series of pilot project calls (specific to DIGILAB, but always interconnected with ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB) to promote real case experimentations in the production and management of digital data within the research question/actors/research protocols/dedicated digital services chain.

YEAR 1: FOUNDATION AND PLANNING

In the first year, the focus would be on establishing the foundation and planning for the implementation of DIGILAB. During the first two quarters, core working groups and governance structures for each layer would be established. Comprehensive surveys and needs assessments within the E-RIHS community would be conducted to gather essential information. By the third and fourth quarters, initial versions of the community-building platform (Layer 0) would be developed, and key stakeholders would be identified. Simultaneously, pilot projects would be initiated to experiment with data lifecycle management and interoperability frameworks (Layer 1). Key activities would include community engagement workshops, preliminary design and development of collaborative platforms, initial data collection and analysis to inform the DIGILAB development, and planning and documentation for pilot projects. These inputs will be used for building schemas for Layers 2 (integrated Virtual Research Environment) and 3 (E-RIHS Knowledge Base).

YEAR 2: INITIAL IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

In the second year, the focus would shift to initial implementation and testing. During the first two quarters, beta versions of the community platform and pilot projects for Layer 1 would be launched. Development of the integration of an integrated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) (Layer 2) would begin. By the third and fourth quarters, the initial implementation of data ingestion, storage, and retrieval systems (Layer 1) would be completed, and interoperability frameworks would be developed and tested in pilot projects. Key activities would include testing and refining the community platform based on user feedback, developing visualisation and annotation tools, implementing data storage and management solutions, and creating initial interoperability frameworks and testing them.

YEAR 3: EXPANSION AND REFINEMENT

The third year would focus on expansion and refinement. During the first two quarters, pilot projects would be expanded to include more diverse datasets and services (coming for pilot projects). Initial development of the integrated VRE would be completed, and user testing would begin (Layer 2). By the third and fourth quarters, comprehensive data indexing and semantic enrichment tools (Layer 1) would be developed, and the initial implementation of the E-RIHS Knowledge Base (Layer 3) would commence. Key activities would include scaling up pilot projects and integrating additional services, refining VRE features and capabilities based on user feedback, developing tools for data selection, indexing, and enrichment, and collecting and structuring data for the knowledge base.

YEAR 4: FULL-SCALE IMPLEMENTATION

In the fourth year, the focus would be on full-scale implementation. During the first two quarters, full versions of the VRE and data lifecycle management systems would be launched. Development and integration of comprehensive search engine and AI-based data processing tools (Layer 3) would be completed. By the third and fourth quarters, the E-RIHS Knowledge Base would be finalised and deployed for community use. Key activities would include final testing and refinement of all tools and services, full deployment of the VRE and associated tools, comprehensive training and support for users and service providers, and continuous data collection and integration into the knowledge base.

YEAR 5: OPTIMISATION AND EVALUATION

The fifth year would focus on optimisation and evaluation. During the first two quarters, a thorough evaluation of all implemented systems and tools would be conducted. Systems would be optimised based on user feedback and performance data. By the third and fourth quarters, next-generation projects and enhancements would be planned and initiated. Key activities would include collecting and analysing user feedback, system optimisation and updates, identifying areas for future development and improvement based on the results and lessons learned from the initial five-year phase.

6 BUSINESS PROCESS MODELLING AND COST ANALYSIS

This chapter describes the general procedure developed for process modelling and cost estimation related to the services offered by DIGILAB in the field of cultural heritage. The main objective is to identify the operational phases of the entire process, pinpoint the process blocks related to information digitisation, define a table and a flexible procedure for estimating service costs, and isolate the costs of the digitisation service from the DIGILAB side. This overarching goal is achieved through the following specific objectives, which are the focus of the conducted research activities:

- Define and standardise the operational processes related to the digitisation of cultural heritage.
- Identify and analyse the blocks of the entire process, focusing on the critical blocks for digitisation.
- Establish a cost estimation methodology specifically for DIGILAB services.
- Validate the methodology through a pilot case study.

6.1 Procedure for Modelling Cultural Heritage Digitisation Processes

The methodology adopted for process analysis is based on the use of Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) 2.0, chosen after a state-of-the-art scouting phase. Researchers from CNR Institute of Heritage Science in Lecce were trained in the use of this tool, utilising the Visual Paradigm software to create BPMN diagrams. The proposed methodology was verified through a pilot case study for validation. The procedure to study and represent a specific process related to the digitisation of cultural heritage is articulated in the following complex phases:

1. Identification of the Service to be Modelled

This preliminary phase is complex and articulated, requiring dialogue between the business expert (business analyst) and domain experts (researchers in the context of cultural heritage). Two scenarios can be distinguished here:

- **Existing Digital Service on Local Research Platforms:** In this case, the service has already been implemented in a digital version and needs to be appropriately migrated to DIGILAB. This entails potential software adjustments at the level of protocols, data access, usage policies, and costs.
- **Existing Service, not yet Digitised:** In this scenario, researchers offer a service related to cultural heritage (e.g., measurements, diagnostics, material analysis, etc.) that needs to be digitised through DIGILAB. This process requires particular attention to the usage policies of the equipment provided (timing, usage modes, etc.) and the production, storage, management, aggregation, and visualisation of the generated data in all its forms and structures.

2. Interview with Key Stakeholders and Domain Experts

This phase involves gathering detailed information through interviews with key stakeholders and service personnel. The interviews aim to gain a thorough understanding of current processes, needs, and challenges.

3. Processing the Interview and Creating the Initial BPMN Diagram

The collected information is processed to create the first version of the BPMN diagram, representing the service process. This initial version serves as a basis for further analysis and optimisation.

4. Identification of Relevant Blocks for Digitisation

The process blocks relevant to data and process digitisation are identified. This includes activities such as scanning, digital archiving, data management, and visualisation.

5. Cost Analysis

For each identified block, a cost analysis is conducted, compiling a table that includes, among other possible cost items characterising the specific case, the following cost items:

- Estimate of personnel costs in terms of man-hours.
- Estimate of any travel expenses on a kilometre basis.
- Setup and amortisation costs of the equipment, increased by a percentage (typically 20-30%) in the case of mobile equipment (MOLAB).
- Personnel costs employed for data digitisation.
- Costs related to proportional data storage.

6. Extraction of Digitisation Activity Costs

The costs related to digitisation activities are extracted, which may correspond to the “digital” blocks of the BPMN diagram alone but may also include connections with blocks not purely related to digitisation but relevant to the final service cost. This analysis provides a detailed view of the specific costs associated with digitisation, isolating direct expenses from indirect ones.

ANNEX

Use Case on Cost Estimation of a Digital Service: A Pilot on Illuminated Manuscripts HUB

The proposed methodology has been tested and validated on a pilot use case related to process definition and cost analysis in the framework of illuminated manuscripts HUB.

The illuminated manuscripts HUB is a project funded by the POR FESR LAZIO 2014/2020 – REGIONE LAZIO, Italy, under the "Gruppi di Ricerca 2020" program. The project was coordinated and implemented by the CNR ISPC (Institute of Heritage Science), as the leader, and the University of Rome Tor Vergata, in collaboration with Biblioteca Angelica, Biblioteca Casanatense di Roma, and the Italian node of MOLAB E-RIHS.IT. The principal investigator of the project was Dr. Eva Pietroni from the CNR ISPC in Rome, Italy. Dr. Pietroni leads a multidisciplinary research team composed of codicologists, paleographers, art historians, conservation scientists, physicians, chemists, biologists, 3D modelers, computer scientists, experts in 3D digitization, communication experts, user experience designers, and metadata specialists.

The goal of the project was to provide the virtual representation of illuminated manuscripts as 3D digital artifacts within a virtual multi-dimensional environment integrating both visible surface elements and hidden sub-surface layers, along with detailed diagnostic data.

The most advanced techniques have been used to digitalize the manuscript:

- Photogrammetry (RGB) to document and model the surface
- Thermography (MWIR) to document sub-surface invisible elements
- Reflectography (MWIR) to facilitate the 3D processing of thermal images

The ATON-based web app providing the illuminated manuscripts digitization service looks like the one shown in Figure 1, exemplified by the case of the "De Balneis Puteolanis".

Figure 1. ATON-based Web App of the illuminated manuscripts HUB

To define the BPMN diagram of the process, the principal investigator of the project and responsible of the service was interviewed. The following main information was extracted during the post-processing phase:

- Selection of manuscripts based on specific criteria
- Selection of poses or configurations of interest in each manuscript
- Manuscript study

Deliverable D5.1

- Design of photogrammetric, reflectographic, and thermographic acquisition set and panel with metric reference
- 4D digitization campaigns
- Interpretation of thermographic images
- Experimentation and application of AI algorithms to increase thermogram resolution and improve orientation on the 3D model
- Photogrammetric processing of models and alignment of RGB and IR textures
- Chemical and microbiological non-destructive analysis
- MOLAB analysis for investigation of pigments and painting materials
- User Research, including "Personas" for detecting user classes and their needs
- Definition of Information Architecture (categories and subcategories)
- User Experience and User Journey Design
- Editorial flow management
- Annotation of models

After post-processing the BPMN diagram of figure 2 was obtained. The diagram includes actors, elementary activities, and all the interactions needed to digitalize a specific illuminated manuscript.

Figure 2. BPMN 2.0 diagram of the Illuminated Manuscripts HUB process.

As a result, the following cost table (Table 1) has been realised merging BPMN diagram information and timing provided by the actors of each single activity.

Table 1. Cost estimation of the elementary activities of Illuminated Manuscripts HUB process

MACRO-ACTIVITY	TEAM	DESCRIPTION	OPERATORS N.	SKILLS	DAYS N.	TRAVEL	SPECIALISED EQUIPMENT	Notes
FIRST MANUSCRIPT DOSSIER	LIBRARY	selection of manuscripts, goals definition, selection of configurations, study of the manuscript. Art and historical context, study of the specific configuration, based on visual analyses, (iconography, writing, structure, material, state of conservation), bibliographic research and collection	3	art historian, palaeographer or codicologist, conservation, supported by a librarian	7 (2 in the library and 5 in laboratory)	possible	no/possible	
4D DATASET ACQUISITION	DATA ACQUISITION	a) design of the acquisition set, b) setting up the acquisition site, c) photogrammetric campaign, d) reflectography and thermography	4	photographer, expert in photogrammetry, expert in MWIR Pulsed-Thermography, supported by a librarian	a) 2 days, b) 0,5 day, c) 0,5 day for ONE CONFIGURATION, d) 0,5 day for ONE CONFIGURATION,	possible	Yes; + 30% of manpower COSTS	
DIAGNOSTIC ANALYSIS	DIAGNOSTICS	Biological, Chemical or Physical analyses carried out in the Library through mobile equipment, aiming at investigating the state of conservation, identification of painting materials and execution techniques	for ONE CONFIGURATION and for each kind of analysis: 2 operators	Biologist, chemist, conservation scientist, art historian	for ONE CONFIGURATION and for each kind of analysis: 12 days. (2 days in the library + 7 days in laboratory + 3 days for coherent integration of results)	Yes (cost estimation considering the distance in Km)	Yes; + 30% of manpower COSTS	some chemical analyses are carried out in external laboratories which can requires several weeks for results.
POST ROCESSING OF THE 4D MODEL & IT TEAM	POST PROCESSING	a) resolution enhancement, b) alignment of RGB and IR dataset, c) textured mesh model production, d) optimization, diagnostic data integration and contextualization	for ONE CONFIGURATION: 2 operators	expert in photogrammetry and in 3d Modeling	a) 0,5 day, b) 1 day, c) 0,5 day, d) 1 day	no	Yes; Datacenter with Repository. 5GB Raw Data for a single Pose	
EDITORIAL WORK	EDITOR	editing of contents based on specific templates, dataset organization, upload of the package on the cloud, annotation in the back-end profile of the webapp	3 operators	expert in digital media, information architecture, editorial flows, publishing	for ONE CONFIGURATION: 7 days	no	no	

The datacenter hosting and running ATON digital resources is characterized by the performance reported in figure 3, where the back-end of the system is also illustrated. Based on available resources, and given the initial setup, running costs of the digital service can be estimated considering the following points:

Figure 3. Back end and characteristics of the datacenter hosting Illuminated Manuscripts HUB Service

1. CPU Utilization:

- The datacenter has 4 CPUs with a frequency of 2400MHz and Bogomips of 4800. The cost estimate must account for the CPU usage time for each process and the associated energy cost.
- **Cost per CPU hour:** Based on an hourly usage rate, considering energy consumption and hardware depreciation.

2. Memory Utilization:

- The cache memory (L1d: 128 KiB, L1i: 128 KiB, L2: 16 MiB) plays a crucial role in performance. The cost should include the amount of memory used and the usage time.
- **Cost per GB of memory per hour:** Based on the actual memory usage and the datacenter operational costs.

3. Storage Utilization:

- Storing digital data requires storage space. The cost is calculated based on the volume of data stored and the duration of storage.
- **Cost per GB of storage per month:** Includes the cost of the storage infrastructure and data management.

4. Network Utilization:

- Data transmission over the network incurs costs for the bandwidth used.
- **Cost per GB of data transfer:** Based on the bandwidth rate and the generated network traffic.

5. Amortization of Equipment:

- The cost of datacenter hardware is amortized over a period.
- **Amortization cost per year:** Based on the initial value of the hardware and the estimated useful life.

6. Operational Costs:

Deliverable D5.1

- Includes the cost of energy, cooling, maintenance, and other operational expenses.
- **Operational cost per hour:** Based on an average of energy and operational costs.

The total service cost can be calculated by summing the costs of the individual digital resources used for running, as better specified in the following example.

Example of Procedure to Estimate the Digital Service Costs

Let's assume to estimate the cost for a DIGILAB service that regularly uses 2 CPUs, 8 GB of memory, 500 GB of storage, and transfers 100 GB of data per month to ensure the digital visualization service of illuminated manuscripts. We assume the following unit costs:

- **CPU:** €0.10 per hour per CPU
- **Memory:** €0.01 per GB per hour
- **Storage:** €0.05 per GB per month
- **Data Transfer:** €0.02 per GB
- **Operational:** €0.50 per hour

The cost estimate will be:

- **CPU:** €0.10 * 2 CPUs = €0.20 per hour
- **Memory:** €0.01 * 8 GB = €0.08 per hour
- **Storage:** €0.05 * 500 GB / 30 = €0.83 per day
- **Data Transfer:** €0.02 * 100 GB = €2.00 per month
- **Operational:** €0.50 per hour

Therefore, the total cost per hour is calculated as follows:

Total Cost per Hour = €0.20 (CPU) + €0.08 (Memory) + (€0.83 / 24) (Storage) + (€2.00 / 720) (Data Transfer) + €0.50 (Operational) ≈ €0.85

This cost estimation procedure provides a detailed overview of the digital resources employed and the related costs for running the selected service. It could serve as a guideline for estimating the costs of other services linked to the DIGILAB.

REFERENCES

- Bender, E.M., Gebru, T., McMillan-Major, A. and Shmitchell, S., (2021). On the dangers of stochastic parrots: Can language models be too big?. In: *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*, pp. 610-623.
- Bertrand, L., et al. (2020) E-RIHS PP D9.3 E-RIHS Scientific Strategy. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4045832.
- Gibson, A., Castillejo, M., Carmona, P., Anglos, D., Ropret, P., Radvan, R., Padfield, J., Fremout, W., Schmidle, W. and Sotiropoulou, S., (2023). IPERION HS D6.3 Final report on innovation, exploitation and interoperability (1.0). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7849169.
- Hermon, S., (2020). Appendix I: Digital Implementation Strategy. In: L. Pezzati, ed. 2020. In: *E-RIHS Implementation Plan v1.0*. With contributions by M. Castillejo, O. De Giacomo, S. Hermon, J.-M. Mimoso, M. Strlic. Revised by J. Striova.
- Hermon, S. (2021). Building DIGILAB – towards data-driven research in cultural heritage. In Hook, D. (ed.) *Virtual Archeology. Revealing the Past, Enriching the Present and Shaping the Future*, pp. 93-106
- Padfield, J. and Degl’Innocenti, E., 2019. DIGILAB’s conceptual plan. Presentation at Evora (January) and Paris (October).
- Padfield, J., Fremout, W., Schmidle, W. and Sotiropoulou, S., (2022). Interim report on documentation of instrument parameters and analysis protocols across access platforms, and metadata requirements (1.2). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7101169.
- Réby, K., Guillem, A., and De Luca, L., (2023). Semantic Segmentation using Foundation Models for Cultural Heritage: an Experimental Study on Notre-Dame de Paris. In: *4th ICCV Workshop on Electronic Cultural Heritage*, Oct 2023, Paris, France. [hal-04275454](#).